

RESPONSE OF COMPOSITE PLATES
TO BLAST LOADING

Victor Birman
School of Naval Architecture and Marine Engineering,
University of New Orleans,
New Orleans, LA 70148
USA

and

Charles W. Bert
School of Aerospace, Mechanical and Nuclear Engineering,
University of Oklahoma,
Norman, OK 73019,
USA

ABSTRACT

Response of simply supported antisymmetrically laminated angle-ply plates to explosive blast loading is considered. A closed-form solution is obtained, it being assumed that the material remains in the elastic range. The effect of transverse shear deformations on the response is taken into consideration. The analysis yields the nondimensional deflection versus time relationship which can be used to determine the stresses and strains in the layers of the plate.

INTRODUCTION

The damage to structures subjected to a conventional air blast wave is due mainly to the overpressure in the shock wave. This overpressure, i.e., the excess over the atmospheric pressure, increases rapidly on the surface exposed to the blast wave and decreases at a much slower rate. Studies concerned with the response of the structures subjected to blast loading often tended to simplify the phenomenon by employing an idealized (usually rectangular) pressure impulse [1-6]. A realistic blast loading was considered by Houlston, et al. [7]. They recorded the pressure-time history from a test using the pressure values at 70 time points to represent the loading function. Nagaya and Nagai [8] considered dynamic response of an isotropic circular plate in contact with a fluid, the surface of which was

excited by explosive pressure measured experimentally. They did not use an analytical expression for the pressure; instead values for a number of sample points were used for the analysis.

The response of simply supported orthotropic plates to blast-type loading was first discussed by Dobyns [9] who considered the response to pulses of different shapes (sine load, step load, triangular load, exponential load, and stepped triangular load). Rajamani and Prabhakaran considered the response of clamped composite plates to blast loading approximated by a rectangular overpressure pulse [10].

An analytical expression for the overpressure-time relationship was given recently by Gupta [11], who used the modified Friedlander exponential decay equation. An approximate solution was obtained for an elastic simply supported plate. A similar problem was solved numerically using the ADINA FEM code [12].

In this paper is studied the response of antisymmetrically laminated angle-ply simply supported plates to conventional blast loading. The effect of shear deformations, which was shown to be significant in dynamic problems of thick composite plates [13,14], is taken into consideration. The closed-form solution is obtained using the convolution integral; the accuracy of this solution is limited only by the number of terms retained in the Fourier series representing displacements and bending slopes. Following the results of [13], the in-plane and rotatory inertias are neglected.

ANALYSIS

An antisymmetrically laminated angle-ply plate of rectangular planform is considered to be subjected to normal pressure $q(x,y,t)$. The equations of motion of such a plate in rectangular coordinates (x,y) are:

$$\begin{aligned} N_{1,x} + N_{6,y} = 0 & \quad ; \quad N_{6,x} + N_{2,y} = 0 & \quad ; \quad Q_{x,x} + Q_{y,y} = \rho h w_{,tt} - q(x,y,t) \\ M_{1,x} + M_{6,y} - Q_x = 0 & \quad ; \quad M_{6,x} + M_{2,y} - Q_y = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where h is the plate thickness, M_i are the stress couples, N_i and Q_i are the in-plane and transverse shear stress resultants respectively, t is time, w is normal deflection, ρ is material density, and $()_{,x}$ denotes $\partial() / \partial x$.

The stress resultants and stress couples are related to the generalized displacements by the constitutive relations:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_1 \\ N_2 \\ N_6 \\ M_1 \\ M_2 \\ M_6 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 & B_{26} \\ 0 & 0 & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & 0 \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & 0 & 0 & 0 & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u_{,x} \\ v_{,y} \\ v_{,x} + u_{,y} \\ \psi_{x,x} \\ \psi_{y,y} \\ \psi_{y,x} + \psi_{x,y} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} Q_y \\ Q_x \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} k_4^2 A_{44} & 0 \\ 0 & k_5^2 A_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} w_{,y} + \psi_y \\ w_{,x} \psi_x \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where k_4^2 and k_5^2 are the shear correction coefficients; A_{ij} , B_{ij} , and D_{ij} are the transformed reduced extensional, coupling, and bending stiffnesses, respectively.

Substitution of the constitutive equations (2,3) into equations of motion (1) yields the set of equations:

$$[L_{k\ell}] \begin{Bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \\ h\psi_y \\ h\psi_x \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \rho h w_{,tt} - q(x,y,t) \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where the elements of symmetric matrix $L_{k\ell}$ are

$$\begin{aligned} L_{11} &= A_{11} d_x^2 + A_{66} d_y^2 & L_{13} &= 0 \\ L_{12} &= (A_{12} + A_{66}) d_x d_y & L_{14} &= (B_{16}/h) d_x^2 + (B_{26}/h) d_y^2 \\ L_{15} &= (2B_{16}/h) d_x d_y & L_{25} &= L_{14} \\ L_{22} &= A_{66} d_x^2 + A_{22} d_y^2 & L_{33} &= -k_5^2 A_{55} d_x^2 - k_4^2 A_{44} d_y^2 \\ L_{23} &= 0 & L_{34} &= -(k_4^2 A_{44}/h) d_y \\ L_{24} &= (2B_{26}/h) d_x d_y & L_{35} &= -(k_5^2 A_{55}/h) d_x \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_{44} &= (D_{66}/h^2)d_x^2 + (D_{22}/h^2)d_y^2 - (k_4^2 A_{44}/h^2) \\
 L_{45} &= (D_{12} + D_{66})h^{-2}d_x d_y \\
 L_{55} &= (D_{11}/h^2)d_x^2 + (D_{22}/h^2)d_y^2 - (k_5^2 A_{55}/h^2) \\
 d_i &= \partial(\dots)/\partial i, \quad i = x, y
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

The simple-support boundary conditions considered here are generalizations of Almroth's S3 conditions [15] or Hoff's SS2 conditions [16]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u(0, y) = u(a, y) = 0 & \quad ; \quad N_6(x, 0) = N_6(x, b) = 0 \\
 N_6(0, y) = N_6(a, y) = 0 & \quad ; \quad v(x, 0) = v(x, b) = 0 \\
 w(0, y) = w(a, y) = 0 & \quad ; \quad w(x, 0) = w(x, b) = 0 \\
 M_1(0, y) = M_1(a, y) = 0 & \quad ; \quad M_2(x, 0) = M_2(x, b) = 0 \\
 \psi_y(0, y) = \psi_y(a, y) = 0 & \quad ; \quad \psi_x(x, 0) = \psi_x(x, b) = 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

These boundary conditions were used by Whitney and Leissa [17], Bert and Chen [13], and Bert and Birman [14]. Both the boundary conditions and the equations of motion (4) can be satisfied exactly by the following representation of displacements and transverse slopes:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u &= \sum_{m,n} U_{mn}(t) \sin \alpha_m x \cos \beta_n y & h\psi_y &= \sum_{m,n} Y_{mn}(t) \sin \alpha_m x \cos \beta_n y \\
 v &= \sum_{m,n} V_{mn}(t) \cos \alpha_m x \sin \beta_n y & h\psi_x &= \sum_{m,n} X_{mn}(t) \cos \alpha_m x \sin \beta_n y \\
 w &= \sum_{m,n} W_{mn}(t) \sin \alpha_m x \sin \beta_n y
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where $\alpha_m = m\pi/a$, $\beta_n = n\pi/b$, m and n being the number of halfwaves along the x and y axes, respectively.

Substitution of the series (7) into equations (4) results in the independent sets of five equations for each set of modal parameters m and n :

$$\begin{aligned}
 C_{11}U_{mn} + C_{12}V_{mn} + C_{14}Y_{mn} + C_{15}X_{mn} &= 0 \\
 C_{12}U_{mn} + C_{22}V_{mn} + C_{24}Y_{mn} + C_{14}X_{mn} &= 0 \\
 (\rho h^2/E_T)\ddot{W}_{mn} + C_{33}W_{mn} - C_{34}Y_{mn} - C_{35}X_{mn} &= (h/E_T)q_{mn}(t) \\
 C_{14}U_{mn} + C_{24}V_{mn} + C_{34}W_{mn} + C_{44}Y_{mn} + C_{45}X_{mn} &= 0 \\
 C_{15}U_{mn} + C_{14}V_{mn} + C_{35}W_{mn} + C_{45}Y_{mn} + C_{55}X_{mn} &= 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where $(\ddot{}) = d^2()/dt^2$.

The nondimensional coefficients C_{ij} coincide with those in [14] except C_{33} (see the Appendix).

$$q_{mn}(t) = (4/ab) \int_0^a \int_0^b q(x,y,t) \sin \alpha_m x \sin \beta_n y \, dx \, dy \quad (9)$$

Transformations similar to those described in [14] reduce the set (8) to a single differential equation:

$$(\rho h^2/E_T) \ddot{W}_{mn} + (K_5^2 \bar{A}_{55} \alpha_{1m}^2 + k_4^2 \bar{A}_{44} \beta_{1n}^2 - F_1 - F_2) W_{mn} = (h/E_T) q_{mn}(t) \quad (10)$$

where $\alpha_{1m} = m\pi h/a$, $\beta_{1n} = n\pi h/b$. The nondimensional stiffnesses \bar{A}_{44} and \bar{A}_{55} and the nondimensional functions F_1 and F_2 are given in the Appendix.

The squared natural frequency of vibration associated with m and n halfwaves of deformation along the x and y axes respectively is immediately obtained from equation (10) being

$$\omega_{mn}^2 = (E_T/\rho h^2) (k_5^2 \bar{A}_{55} \alpha_{1m}^2 + k_4^2 \bar{A}_{44} \beta_{1n}^2 - F_1 - F_2) \quad (11)$$

The equation of motion (10) can be represented in the nondimensional form:

$$\frac{d^2 \bar{W}_{mn}}{d\tau^2} + \bar{\omega}_{mn}^2 \bar{W}_{mn} = \bar{q}_{mn}(\tau) \quad (12)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{W}_{mn} &= W_{mn}/h & \tau &= \omega_{11} t \\ \bar{\omega}_{mn} &= \omega_{mn}/\omega_{11} & \bar{q}_{mn} &= q_{mn}/\rho h^2 \omega_{11}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

The response $\bar{W}_{mn}(\tau)$ is obtained using the convolution integral:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{W}_{mn}(\tau) &= A_{mn} \sin \bar{\omega}_{mn} \tau + B_{mn} \cos \bar{\omega}_{mn} \tau \\ &+ (1/\bar{\omega}_{mn}) \int_0^\tau \bar{q}_{mn}(v) \sin \bar{\omega}_{mn}(\tau - v) \, dv \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where A_{mn} and B_{mn} are constants of integration. The plate being at rest when loaded by the blast pressure, one can express the initial conditions as

$$\bar{W}_{mn}(0) = 0, \quad \frac{d\bar{W}_{mn}}{d\tau}(0) = 0 \quad (15)$$

The first condition (15) yields $B_{mn} = 0$.

The blast wave reaches the peak value in such a short time that the structure is usually assumed to be loaded instantly. Furthermore, experiments indicate that the pressure can be considered uniformly distributed over the plate [7]. The overpressure-time relationship can be represented by the modified Friedlander exponential decay equation [11,12]:

$$q(x,y,t) = q_p(1 - t/t_p) e^{-a't/t_p} \quad (16)$$

where q_p is the peak reflected pressure in excess of the ambient pressure, t_p is the positive phase duration of the impulse, and a' is a coefficient. Therefore, the nondimensional pressure in equation (14) is

$$\bar{q}_{mn}(v) = \frac{16}{mn\pi^2} \bar{q} \left(1 - \frac{v}{\tau_p}\right) e^{-a'v/\tau_p} \quad (17)$$

where $\bar{q} = q_p/\rho h^2 \omega_{11}^2$, τ_p being the nondimensional duration of the positive phase, i.e., $\tau_p = \omega_{11} t_p$. Substitution of equation (17) into equation (14) and the satisfaction of the second condition (15) yield

$$\begin{aligned} W_{mn}(\tau) = & \frac{16\bar{q}}{mn\pi^2\bar{\omega}_{mn}} \frac{1}{(a'/\tau_p)^2 + \bar{\omega}_{mn}^2} \left\{ e^{-a'\tau/\tau_p} \left(1 - \frac{\tau}{\tau_p}\right) \bar{\omega}_{mn} \right. \\ & + (a'/\tau_p) \sin \bar{\omega}_{mn} \tau - \bar{\omega}_{mn} \cos \bar{\omega}_{mn} \tau \\ & - \frac{1}{[(a'/\tau_p)^2 + \bar{\omega}_{mn}^2] \tau_p} [2(a'/\tau_p) \bar{\omega}_{mn} e^{-a'\tau/\tau_p} \\ & \left. + ((a'/\tau_p)^2 - \bar{\omega}_{mn}^2) \sin \bar{\omega}_{mn} \tau - 2(a'/\tau_p) \bar{\omega}_{mn} \cos \bar{\omega}_{mn} \tau] \right\} \quad (18) \end{aligned}$$

PLATE STRENGTH

The present solution is valid so long as the plate remains in the elastic range. Therefore, it is important to detect the moment when the stresses in a part of the plate reach the combination prescribed by yield criteria. In the case of simply supported plates, plastic effects first appear in the center: $x = a/2$, $y = b/2$. It can be easily seen that the nonzero stress couples in the center are M_1 and M_2 ; the only nonzero stress resultant is N_6 . Therefore, transverse shear deformability does not influence directly the yield condition. However, this influence exists

through the solution $w(t)$ which depends on shear correction.

Maximum stresses at the faces of the plate are:

$$\sigma_x + \pm 6 M_1/h^2 \quad ; \quad \sigma_y = \pm 6 M_2/h^2 \quad ; \quad \tau_{xy} = N_6/h \quad (19)$$

These stresses are related to the stresses in the principal material directions by the transformation relation:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c^2 & s^2 & 2sc \\ s^2 & c^2 & -2sc \\ -sc & sc & c^2 - s^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

where $c = \cos \theta$, $s = \sin \theta$. Once the stresses σ_1 , σ_2 , τ_{12} are calculated, the Tsai-Hill yield criterion can be used to detect the instant of plasticity initiation [18]:

$$(\sigma_1^2/X^2) - (\sigma_1 \sigma_2/X^2) + (\sigma_2^2/Y^2) + (\tau_{12}^2/S^2) = 1 \quad (21)$$

where X and Y are failure strengths for a lamina in the axial and transverse directions, respectively; S is the shear failure strength.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

The response of the laminated plates with an aspect ratio equal to 2 and lamination angle $\pm 30^\circ$ is shown in Figs. 1,2. The material of the plates is graphite/epoxy with the following nondimensional characteristics: $E_L/E_T = 40$, $G_{LT}/E_T = 0.5$, $G_{LZ}/E_T = G_{TZ}/E_T = 0.6$, $\nu_{LT} = 0.25$. The shear correction coefficients are $k_4^2 = k_5^2 = 5/6$. The blast parameters are taken as $a' = 1.98$, $t_p = 0.004$ sec [12]. The response of two plates consisting of four super layers* with a total laminate thickness of 1 inch is shown in Fig. 1. The response of 1-in.-thick multilayer plates which do not exhibit bending-stretching coupling (i.e., many alternating angle-ply layers) is shown in Fig. 2. In all cases, the nondimensional amplitude of the load is $\bar{q} = 0.1$. Note that the curves in Figs. 1,2 are not comparable since the values of \bar{q} and τ depend on the plate natural frequencies ω_{11} which are different. However, the general tendency is the same for all plates. The deflection reaches a maximum value after which it decreases. If one

* The term "super layer" is used here to mean a set of many parallel unidirectional layers. For example, if each super layer consists of twenty layers, then the total laminate thickness is equal to eighty layers.

continues the analysis for larger values of the nondimensional time τ , the response appears to be oscillatory and the effect of damping should be taken into account. These oscillations are not shown in Figs. 1,2 since the maximum deflection which is reached almost immediately after the blast is more important.

CONCLUSION

An exact expression for the response of shear deformable composite plates subjected to air-blast loading modeled by the modified Friedlander exponential decay equation has been obtained by use of the convolution integral. Results for several differential classes of layups were presented in dimensionless form.

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APPENDIX: SOME COEFFICIENTS

$$C_{33} = k_5^2 \bar{A}_{55} \alpha_{lm}^2 + k_4^2 \bar{A}_{44} \beta_{ln}^2 \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where

$$\bar{A}_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n \bar{Q}_{ij}(k)/n \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$F_1 = C_{35}(C_{35}S_6 - C_{34}S_5)/\bar{S} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$F_2 = C_{34}(C_{34}S_7 - C_{35}S_5)/\bar{S}$$

where S_5, \dots, S_8 are as given in Ref. 14 and

$$\bar{S} = S_5S_8 - S_6S_7. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Figure 1. Dimensionless response of four-super-layer ($+30^\circ/-30^\circ/+30^\circ/-30^\circ$) plates to blast loading. Solid curve is for a thin plate ($h/a = 0.025$) and dashed curve is for a thicker plate ($h/a = 0.050$).

Figure 2. Dimensionless response of many-layer alternating angle-ply ($\pm 30^\circ$) plates to blast loading. Solid curve is for a thin plate ($h/a = 0.025$) and dashed curve is for a thicker plate ($h/a = 0.050$).